

Highly transparent aluminum silicon oxy nitride permeation barriers for optoelectronic devices[☆]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Permeation barrier
Flexible electronics
Magnetron sputtering

ABSTRACT

We investigate the properties of sputtered aluminum silicon oxynitride layers for application as transparent permeation barrier front sheets for flexible opto-electronic applications. We compare the results from mixed aluminum-silicon and pure silicon targets when the reactive gas content is varied in a dynamic roll-to-roll process on the optical, structural, permeation properties of the layers. We observe that permeation barrier layers deposited from mixed aluminum-silicon targets shows a change in layer growth and the resulting properties compared with layers from a pure silicon Target.

1. Introduction

The advantage of flexible optoelectronics is the freedom of system design combined with low weight and the potential to produce at high throughput and low-cost. To ensure the longevity of these devices, it is necessary to protect them from the effects of oxygen and water vapor. For this purpose, they will be encapsulated with a transparent permeation barrier front sheet. To ensure the longevity of organic solar cells, for example, a water vapor transmission rate of less than $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ g/(m²•d) is required [1].

Polymer films coated with metal oxides, metal nitrides or mixed forms have been widely investigated for permeation barrier applications [2–11] as they can be deposited in industry relevant processes, i.e. as a single layer in a dynamic large area coating process using reactive magnetron sputtering [10]. Other processes for producing thin metal oxide or metal nitride layers are high-rate evaporation [12], atomic layer deposition (ALD) [3,4,13,14] or ion beam assisted deposition (IBAD) [12,15]. In the case of permeation barrier layers for flexible optoelectronics, the demands are stringent, and the material system must combine excellent encapsulation against oxygen and water vapor with high transparency and mechanical flexibility.

The permeation properties of single layers depend on the layer microstructure and are mainly determined by defects [9]. These defects can relate to the underlying substrate, the coating process, or the coating material itself. In crystalline materials, grain boundaries form

preferential paths for gas diffusion. In contrast, amorphous materials are less dense but also do not contain these grain boundary diffusion pathways [16]. Further, thicker layers reduce diffusion rates but also the optical transparency of the layer and generally increases brittleness. Finally, in addition to film thickness and microstructure, the chemical composition of the film will further impact the optical properties as well as the mechanical and thermal properties.

In this study, we optimize the deposition process for aluminum silicon oxynitride layers to achieve the desired permeation barrier properties. We exploit a dynamic deposition process to fabricate coatings with a gradient in chemical composition [17]. This allows us to systematically vary individual process parameters and correlate these with layer composition.

Table 1 summarizes the relevant properties for flexible permeation barrier films for pure oxides and pure nitrides. The figures are quantitative, as they depend on many factors such as the substrate material used or the layer thickness. Our aim is to develop a mixed oxynitride layer that optimally combines high transparency, low water vapor permeability and high flexibility. While nitridic compounds tend to have a lower water vapor permeability, oxidic compounds have a higher transparency. On the other hand, aluminum nitride (AlN) and Silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) have relatively high mechanical flexibility.

[☆] This article is part of a Special issue entitled: 'PSE 2024' published in Surface & Coatings Technology.

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Table 1

Material comparison of main properties for permeation barriers in optoelectronic applications of Al₂O₃, AlN, SiO₂ and Si₃N₄.

Property	Al ₂ O ₃	AlN	SiO ₂	Si ₃ N ₄
Permeation barrier properties	Good gas barrier [2–5]	Excellent gas barrier [6,7]	Good gas barrier [11,18]	Superior gas barrier [8]
Optical properties	Transparent in visible range [3,12]	Less transparent than Al ₂ O ₃ [19–21]	Transparent in visible range [22]	Less transparent than SiO ₂ [23–25]
Chemical properties	Not stable in contact with water [26]	Not stable in contact with water [27]	Stable in contact with water [28,29]	Stable in contact with water [29]
Mechanical properties	Flexible in thin films [30,31]	Hard, brittle [32]	Hard, brittle [33]	Hard, brittle [33,34]

2. Experimental

The properties of permeation barriers depend largely on the quality of the substrate material [1]. A 100 µm PET Melinex® grade PCS from Dupont Tejin Film was used here. This material has a 25 µm protective film that is produced by co-extrusion during manufacture and thus protects the surface from environmental influences.

Permeation barrier coatings are deposited in a reactive magnetron sputtering process in a roll-to-roll process in the pilot web coater *coFlex®600* at Fraunhofer FEP [9,10]. In the vacuum chamber, the protective film was removed from substrate material immediately before coating by Double magnetron systems with rotatable targets.

Constant process parameters were used for each composition. The layer thickness was adjusted by varying the web speed in the range of 0.5 m/min to 1.3 m/min. A constant sputtering power of 20 kW was used for the coating and the process was voltage-regulated. This means that a voltage was specified, and the inlet of the reactive gas is adjusted until the set voltage is reached. The composition of the reactive gas was varied to produce different sample compositions. From 100 % oxygen in increments of 10 % up to 100 % nitrogen. The operating point was determined by analyzing the hysteresis. Starting from the oxidic mode, the voltage was gradually reduced until the transition mode was reached after the reversal point. Fig. 1 shows the total gas flow of oxygen and nitrogen as a function of the sputter voltage. The shape of the hysteresis curves changes depending on the gas composition. This can be explained by the occupation of the target surface by oxides or nitrides and their respective sputtering properties. It can also be seen that the curve shifts from the pure silicon target (Fig. 1a) to lower gas flows due to the

aluminum content (Fig. 1b) and the curves are compressed.

The selection criterion for the operating point, marked in Fig. 1, was the highest possible transparency (oxidic mode) with the highest possible deposition rate (metallic mode). Accordingly, the operating point was determined to be the point in transition mode close to the switch to oxidic mode.

In a separate experiment, a 25 µm PE-based film was applied immediately after coating. This film protects the coating from damage caused by roller contact in the further course of the process. In addition, the film has a strong adhesion to the coating and cannot be removed without detaching parts of the coating from the substrate. It therefore remains on the sample during the measurement of the water vapor transmission rate (WVTR). PE also exhibits hydrophobic behavior, which can influence permeation.

3. Methods

For WVTR measurements, layers of identical thickness were produced to investigate the influence of the composition on the WVTR independently of the layer thickness.

The WVTR measurements were carried out in accordance to the ISO 15106-3 standard at a temperature of 38 °C and 90 % relative humidity. WDDG (Brugger) measuring devices were used for this purpose. The size of the measuring area is 78.5 cm².

Both spectral transmission and reflection are measured using the Lambda 1050 spectrophotometer from Perkin Elmer. The measurement range extends from 250 nm to 1500 nm with an increment of $\Delta\lambda = 2$ nm. To obtain a comparable measured value between the individual transmission spectra, the light transmittance is calculated for the visible wavelength range (T_{vis}), based on DIN EN 410.

$$T_{vis} = \frac{\int_{\lambda=380 \text{ nm}}^{780 \text{ nm}} T(\lambda) \bullet V(\lambda) \bullet \Delta\lambda}{\int_{\lambda=380 \text{ nm}}^{780 \text{ nm}} V(\lambda) \bullet \Delta\lambda}$$

X-ray reflectometry (XRR) analyses were carried out to check layer thickness of the samples produced. For this purpose, samples with a removable protective film were applied to a glass lens carrier under cleanroom conditions using a pressure-sensitive adhesive (PSA). This is necessary to generate a plane-parallel surface from the flexible substrate for this measuring method. The measurements were carried out on a D8 diffractometer from Bruker. Cu-K α radiation was used for the measurement and a 0D detector type LynxEye was used. Work was carried out in coupled two theta/theta mode.

Cross-sections and fracture images were examined by a high resolution field emission scanning electron microscope SU 8000 from

Fig. 1. The hysteresis curves from sputter voltage versus gas flow were monitored for process development. The gas flow adjustment is a function of the specified process voltage from the a) 100 wt% silicon target and b) 50 wt% silicon 50 wt% aluminum target.

Fig. 2. Transmission properties of SiO_xN_y and Al₅₀Si₅₀O_xN_y samples on a PET substrate fabricated at operating point in different working gas compositions. Each layer had the same layer thickness. a) Transmission spectra of SiO_xN_y, b) transmission spectra of Al₅₀Si₅₀O_xN_y and c) transmission in visible range (included 380 nm–780 nm) measured.

Fig. 3. Layer thickness determination by a) cross section SiO_x150 nm, b) cross section SiN_y 93 nm and c) via X-ray reflectometry.

Table 2

Layer thicknesses used for validation. Determined with SEM and XRR as well as the respective percentage deviation and the range of deviation.

SEM thickness [nm]	XRR thickness [nm]	Deviation [%]
159 ± 3	152 ± 1	4.4
150 ± 3	145 ± 1	3.3
130 ± 3	125 ± 1	3.8
117 ± 3	112 ± 1	3.9
114 ± 3	110 ± 1	4.0
113 ± 3	109 ± 1	3.0
93 ± 3	92 ± 1	1.1

Hitachi to validate the layer thickness and to assess the layer structure. The Cross-Section Polisher, SM-09010 from Jeol was used for the preparation of ion-polished cross-sections. A 6 kV argon ion beam with a half-width of 500 μm is aligned perpendicular to a shielding plate and the sample surface. The part of the sample protruding below the shielding plate has a width of about 75 μm and is ablated by the Ar ion beam by sputtering, while the rest of the sample is protected from ion ablation by the shielding plate. To avoid the well-known curtain effect, the sample is also oscillated by ±45°. The prepared cross-section has a width of up to about 1 mm.

Chemical depth profiles of the layers were investigated by glow discharge optical emission spectroscopy (GD-OES) using the GD-Profilier 2 from HORIBA Jobin Yvon. The layers are sputtered using a rf glow discharge whereas the intensities of optical emission lines are simultaneously measured versus sputtering time.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Optical properties

The transmission was measured for all compositions for samples of identical film thickness. Fig. 2 shows the transmission properties of SiO_xN_y (Fig. 2a) and Al₅₀Si₅₀O_xN_y (Fig. 2b) samples. The spectra show that the transmission decreases over the entire spectral range as the nitrogen content in the reaction gas increases. The UV cut at 380 nm comes directly from the substrate material. In Fig. 2c shows the transmission averaged over the visible wavelength range. This shows that the transmission decreases with increasing nitrogen content, as previously reported in Table 1 for static processes. The layers deposited from the pure silicon target show a stronger influence of the nitrogen content on the transmission than the layers deposited from the aluminum-silicon mixed target.

4.2. Structural properties

Fig. 3 shows results of the layer thickness determination of selected SiO_xN_y samples. The error in the coating thickness determined in this way is given as ±3 nm due to the resolution of the microscope. On the one hand directly determined by an SEM cross-section (Fig. 3a & b), on the other by XRR (Fig. 3c). The critical angle for total internal reflection can be used to derive the electron density very close to the surface. As is known from the literature, the layers deposited in the dynamic process have a gradient in chemical composition [17]. This means that this does not provide any information about the density of the entire layer. The film thickness was determined from the reflectograms using the following equation:

$$d \approx \frac{\lambda}{2n_{osc}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\sin\theta_2)^2 - (\sin\theta_c)^2} - \sqrt{(\sin\theta_1)^2 - (\sin\theta_c)^2}}$$

where λ is the wavelength of the radiation used, n_{osc} is the number of oscillations, θ_c is the angle of critical reflection, θ₁ is the angle of the first minimum and θ₂ is the angle of the last minimum.

The calculated value of the layer thickness for silicon oxide (violet

Fig. 4. Dynamic growth rates as a function of nitrogen content for pure silicon target and aluminum-silicon mixed target.

Fig. 5. WVTR at 38 °C/90 % r.h. depending on the working gas composition for samples from silicon target (magenta points) and from aluminum silicon target (blue points). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

line) is 145 ± 1 nm. This was confirmed on a cross-sectional image of the same sample with 150 ± 3 nm (Fig. 3a). Similarly, a layer thickness of 92 ± 1 nm was calculated for silicon nitride (magenta line) and 93 ± 3 nm was measured (Fig. 3b). Table 2 shows the coating thicknesses determined for all samples on which both methods were carried out. The table also shows the deviations between the coating thicknesses of the methods. The average deviation of the samples is between 1.1 % and 4.4 %. That means of XRR measurement is therefore permissible.

Due to the gradients that arise in dynamically deposited layers, which were investigated by Himmler et al. and described in an optical 5-layer model [17], it was initially unclear whether the layer thickness of such layers could be determined with XRR. This has made it possible to establish a simple and inexpensive measuring method for determining the layer thicknesses of such gradient layers.

The dynamic growth rate (Fig. 4) was determined from the coating thicknesses determined and the web speeds used during the coating process. The lines shown are for illustration purposes only. A physical

Fig. 6. SEM fracture images of a) silicon oxide b) silicon oxynitride c) silicon nitride d) aluminum-silicon oxide e) aluminum-silicon oxynitride f) aluminum-silicon nitride.

Fig. 7. Result of GD-OES measurement on a 600 nm thick layer sputtered from $Al_{50}Si_{50}$ -Target with gas composition of 75% O_2 and 25 % N_2 .

relationship has not yet been investigated. When working with a pure silicon target (Fig. 4 magenta points), the dynamic growth rate decreases strongly with the nitrogen content. In contrast, when using an aluminum-silicon mixed target (Fig. 4 blue points), the dynamic growth rate falls less quickly. This indicates that the growth mechanism is altered by the aluminum content. The fact that the coating rate decreases with increasing nitrogen content is partly due to the lower affinity of nitrogen for oxygen based on the lower electronegativity. On

the other hand, AlN forms on the target surface itself, which reduces the sputter yield.

4.3. Permeation barrier properties

We selected samples with the same thickness ($120 \text{ nm} \pm 5 \text{ nm}$) for water vapor transmission (WVTR) measurements. The results are shown in Fig. 5. In case of coatings from pure silicon target (magenta points),

we observe an increase in the WVTR when the films are increasingly oxidic. This is in line with the known literature from Table 1. In the case of silicon aluminum-based coatings (blue points), no trend is observed when varying the working gas content. This indicates that the layer structure is influenced by aluminum content.

Fig. 6 shows fracture images. The oxide layers (Fig. 6a & d) show a smoother fracture than the nitride layers (Fig. 6c & f), corresponding to the respective mechanical properties given in Table 1. It can also be seen that the nitridic layers grow in columnar structures. The visual appearance suggests that the pure silicon oxide (Fig. 6a) layer may have a higher porosity at the surface compared with silicon nitride (Fig. 6c) but also compared with aluminum silicon oxide (Fig. 6d).

4.4. Chemical properties

Using GD-OES (Fig. 7), it was possible to show that the behavior of oxygen and nitrogen within an AlSiO_xN_y layer is analogous to that in a SiO_xN_y layer from the literature [17]. Due to the process, zones of different plasma density form over the double magnetron. As a result, oxidic depositions occur preferentially at the outer edges and between the targets, while nitride depositions occur preferentially directly above the targets. The moving substrate produces the profile shown. In addition, it is noticeable that the course of the aluminum content within the layer follows that of the nitrogen. In contrast, the silicon content within the layer is almost constant. This process does not lead to a structure that can be recognized in the fracture images (Fig. 6e).

5. Conclusion

In this study we examine aluminum silicon oxynitride sputtered in a dynamic roll-to-roll process. The properties of our pure oxide and nitride layers are consistent with results from layers prepared using static processes in the literature. We show the impact of the reactive gas content on the WVTR properties of the coatings. While for pure silicon targets, we observe an increase in WVTR with increased oxygen content. We demonstrate that for mixed aluminum-silicon targets, the reactive gas content has no influence of WVTR. Further, by monitoring the growth rates of the films, we show that the aluminum content in the target influences the growth mechanism, as evidenced in the microstructure of the layer. With the methods shown in this work, it is only possible to determine the density close to the surface. In future, a suitable measuring method will be used to determine density in depth resolution. Since it is known from literature that flexibility can be increased by an aluminum content in the coating system, it is necessary to show this in further investigations, e.g. by means of roll bending tests.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patrick Schlenz: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cindy Steiner:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition. **Olaf Zywitzki:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Elizabeth von Hauff:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

The results were produced as part of the EU Horizon 2020 funded BOOSTER project (grant agreement No 952911) and the Horizon Europe funded PEARL project (grant agreement No 101122283).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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